

IMPROVEMENT OF PSYCHOLOGICAL AND PEDAGOGICAL COMPETENCES OF KOMRAT STATE UNIVERSITY ACADEMIC STAFF IN THE LIFELONG LEARNING SYSTEM

Sergei ZAHARIYA

Universitatea de Stat din Comrat

In accordance with the modern educational demands the professional training of university teachers is strictly required. The requirements for the lecturer's psycho-pedagogical competence are constantly becoming more and more complex. A competent approach of the modern specialists training is of a major importance in both the problem of forming the students' socio-professional competencies and the development of the lecturers' psychological-pedagogical skills. New forms and methods of training based on computer technology are becoming widespread within universities. The implementation of information technology in the higher school educational process generates a number of new requirements for the professional competencies and abilities of university teachers..

Keywords: *psycho-pedagogical competence; universities; education system; higher education.*

ÎMBUNĂȚIREA COMPETENȚELOR PSIHOLOGICE ȘI PEDAGOGICE ALE PERSONALULUI DIDACTIC AL UNIVERSITĂȚII STATULUI COMRAT ÎN SISTEMUL ÎNVĂȚAREA PE TOT PARCURSUL VIEȚII

In conformitate cu cerințele educaționale moderne, este absolut necesară formarea profesională a profesorilor universitari. Cerințele pentru competența psihopedagogică a cadrelor didactice devin din ce în ce mai complicate. Abordarea competență a formării specialiștilor moderni pune în primă importanță nu numai problema formării competențelor socioprofessionale a studenților, ci și dezvoltarea competenței psiho-pedagogice a cadrelor didactice. Noi forme și metode de formare pe baza tehnologiei informatice devin larg răspândite în universități. Implementarea tehnologiei informației în procesul de învățământ superior generează o serie de cerințe noi pentru competența profesională a profesorului universitar.

Cuvinte-cheie: *competență psiho-pedagogică; universități; sistem educațional; educație înaltă.*

The problem of improving the professional competence of teachers of higher education in recent decades has acquired special significance and has identified current aspects. The pedagogical reality that has developed in the higher school proclaims that the need for the professional training of the university teachers in accordance with modern requirements is urgently needed. The requirements for the teacher's psychological-pedagogical competence are constantly getting complicated, which is caused by a number of reasons.

First, the social procurement for the training of highly qualified personnel capable, that are able to develop an innovative economy and ensuring the competitiveness of the state requires a comprehensive improvement of the educational process in the university, and its quality improving.

Secondly, the integration of education systems, established under the signing of the Bologna Declaration, implies the introduction of innovative approaches to the training of students and, accordingly, submits increased demands on the competence of university teachers. The modern educational paradigm shifts the emphasis from traditional teaching to the control of independent cognitive activities of students, which requires the teacher to master new pedagogical approaches, as well as methods and forms of work.

Thirdly, the informatization of education expands the capabilities of teachers in the transfer of educational knowledge, creates a need for mastering modern information technologies, including distance learning technologies. All this changes the position and role of the teacher in the didactic process of the university, the nature of communicative interaction with students [1].

And, finally, the competence-based approach to the training of modern specialists, provided for by the reform of higher education, places among the top priorities not only the problem of forming the social and professional competencies of students, but also the development of the teacher's psychological and pedagogical competence.

The need for psycho-pedagogical training of teachers in higher education is also dictated by the fact that some of them do not have a basic vocational and pedagogical education. Psychological and pedagogical knowledge is acquired empirically, with the profession mastering, and in many ways are random, unsystematized, and therefore are not a reliable theoretical basis for the successful solution of professional problems.

Thus, in recent years, the tendency to compulsory psychological and pedagogical training of university teachers in the system of additional vocational education increases.

The problem of the competence development of the university teacher has acquired special significance together with the spread of the concept of competence-oriented education, which formed the basis for documents related to the reform of the higher school.

The main goal of the competence-based approach is to strengthen the practical orientation of education, going beyond the limited “knowledge” paradigm. Competent-oriented education, therefore, involves mastering students’ basic methods of working, developing their willingness to flexible and mobile use of the available knowledge, skills, and abilities to solve real-life and professional problems.

The need for students to develop social and professional competencies capable of further successful adaptation and competitiveness in a market economy makes it necessary to look at the problem of the competence of university teachers from a new perspective – how much they themselves have the appropriate set of competencies in order to fulfil more fully imposed on them task of preparing modern specialists.

Considering that the activity of the teacher of higher education is multifunctional and includes not only pedagogical, but also scientific, research, methodological, technical and didactic and other activities, it is advisable to divide professional and pedagogical competence. At the same time, pedagogical competence is an integral part of the teacher’s professional competence. And since education and mentoring presuppose direct communication with students, the use of methods of psychological influence on them, the methods of self-regulation of mental states, etc., it is advisable to use a broader concept – “psycho-pedagogical competence” of a teacher of higher education.

Thus, the competence of a high school teacher is understood to mean the complex of professional knowledge, skills, values, and the willingness to use them for effective implementation of activities.

In the structure of the teacher’s competence, the following components can be distinguished [4]:

1) positive motivation for the competence demonstration (motivational component)

2) knowledge underlying the understanding of the content of activities and the choice of ways to implement it (cognitive component):

3) skills, experience of successful implementation of necessary actions (operational-technological component):

4) axiological representations and the relation to the content and result of activity (the axiological component)

The criteria for assessing the formation of the competence of a university teacher are, therefore, the totality of his professional knowledge, skills, values, which he follows in his activity, and motivational readiness to perform professional functions with a high level of quality.

The social procurement for the training of specialists who must be in demand on the labour market, the changing economic and sociocultural conditions of life, scientific and technological achievements - all this determines the new requirements for the professional activity of the teacher. Thus, for example, the

internationalization of education or the introduction of information technologies of teaching fundamentally changes the pedagogical process in the university and simultaneously facilitates the acquisition by the teacher of new knowledge, the formation of new ways of activity. The expansion of the teacher’s functions eventually is fixed in the qualification characteristic, reflecting the scientifically substantiated composition of professional knowledge, skills and abilities. The qualification characteristic is nothing more than a normative model of professional competence.

The new forms and methods of training on

the basis of computer technology are becoming widespread in universities. We have to state that the introduction of information technology in the higher school educational process advances a number of new requirements for the teacher's professional competence.

First, the importance of technical and didactic training, knowledge of the pedagogical capabilities of information technology increases. In this context, there is a need for readiness for constant improvement in this area.

Secondly, the teacher requires the competence to prepare training courses in their electronic presentation.

Thirdly, the wide opportunities offered by

modern technical means require the teacher the good command of new forms and methods of teaching, first of all, the methodology of lecture-presentation, simulation laboratory work, webinar, chat, teleconference, etc...

The teacher even now has to take into account the new realities of the functioning of high education institutions: an increase in the economic dimension in their activities, an increase of competition, the total introduction of information tools of education, the integration processes in the education field.

Taking into account that the professional competence of the teacher is formed in the activity, it is quite justified to identify the types of competencies in accordance with the types of activity:

The psycho-pedagogical competence of the teacher is demonstrated in his ability and readiness to interact with the students competently, to manage their cognitive activities, communication and simultaneously to regulate their own behaviour and activities. The psycho-pedagogical competence is based on the corresponding knowledge, skills, moral and ideological values and assumes the readiness of their creative realization in professional activity for achieving its high results. The development of the teacher's psycho-pedagogical competence is affected by many factors: the nature of basic vocational training, the natural abilities and inclinations, work motivation, the pedagogical personality orientation.

The psycho-pedagogical competence of the teacher is formed within the professional activity, which directly depends on the educational situation in the country and the world, therefore one it cannot be ignored a number of social factors. The social procurement for the training of specialists capable of developing an innovative economy and ensuring the competitiveness of the state, the drawing together of national higher education systems within the

framework of integration processes, and the wide informatization of education all impose new demands on the teacher's psycho-pedagogical competence. He even now has to develop syllabus taking into account the different levels of student training, to use the information technology training, to focus on the formation of social and professional competencies of graduates, in order to improve their competitiveness in the labour market.

In order to implement the pedagogical idea of the need to build a system for improving the pedagogical skills of teachers at the Comrat State University, a program has been set up to increase the psychological and pedagogical competence of higher school teachers.

In this context, we note that since 2010-2011 academic years the Centre for Life-long Education of Didactic Personnel functions at the university. It is a structural subdivision that implements a wide range of additional educational programs for professional retraining for general and higher education specialists.

One of the directions of the Centre's work is

the organization and realization of the courses on the psycho-pedagogical module since 2014. The courses are oriented for teachers of higher education, didactic cadres of the system of professional and additional education, who do not have special psycho-pedagogical training.

The goal of professional development is the growth of professionalism that can be achieved in the process of solving the following problems:

- motivation of self-development, self-education, professional growth, career;
- the increase of competence: social, psychological, pedagogical, economic, legal, special, etc.;
- the development of psychological properties, professionally important qualities, correction of professional forms of behaviour;
- the development of auto competence (personal competence) and adjustment of the teacher's psycho-professional profile;
- providing conditions for self-development, self-education of the individual [2].

The acquisition of the psycho-pedagogical module is designed to help the teacher to understand the need to eliminate from old stereotypes, change his own professional position on the basis of its reflexive analysis and mastering of modern scientific ideas. This approach contributes to: giving the higher education system steadiness and expediency; the development of teachers' independence and responsibility, self-awareness, leadership and creative attitude to pedagogical activity [3].

The additional reserve is represented by the use of certain technologies of distance education, interactive IT-tools. This became possible as a result of the participation of the teachers of Comrat State University in the European project TEACH ME and the reorganization of the existing Centre for Lifelong Education in the framework of this project in November 2017. The centre is arranged with modern computer equipment that meets the needs of the university. The aim of the project is to prepare innovative and educational proposals for teachers

involved in professional development courses, as well as to increase the attractiveness and access to continuing education by reviewing and adapting the e-learning methodology.

So, the investment potential of the university often depends on the innovative nature of the development of scientific, educational and practical activities of the subjects of the educational process, their involvement in the innovation system. Taking into account these factors, the educational process in Comrat State University is built on the basis of modern educational technologies and organizational forms of education in order to transfer the main emphasis of the learning process to the student, to develop and encourage his initiative, creativity, independence, responsibility for the results of his work.

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